

Aesthetics in Literature:

Expressing the Human Being at the Heart of Politics

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Abstract

Students of political theory in the global West are often taught about liberalism, rationality, and ideology through the writings of Plato, Aristotle, Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, Kant, and other ‘key’ theorists. To be effective political theorists, students are instructed to write essays that assume a basis of human rationality and follow patterns of reason (e.g. deductive rationality) to derive conclusions about the interactions of people with institutions and states. Often excluded from the canon are literary or aesthetic (i.e. stylistic or artistically inspired) works of poetry, novels, and passionately emotive investigations of the tangible self and community. I argue that literary or aesthetic works should be read alongside ‘traditional’ canonical texts to broaden the study of politics and gain a better understanding of human political establishments and resistance within the intimate and unconstrained context of stylistic pieces of writing or artistic prose.

Introduction

Polis, the ancient Greek root of modern “politics,” assumes the existence of a state and series of institutions built around the community of a *polity*. Implicit in this is an assumption of relationality between the people of the community and the institutions they establish in a variety of state systems. These relationships are constituted by human beings who are navigating their position with themselves, others, the authority-giving collective, and the government through dual emotional (i.e. based on feeling and instinct) and rational (i.e. based on logical analysis) capacities. Therefore, the theory of politics, as a philosophical study of the social and institutional relationships that constitute politics, requires a dichotomous understanding of the emotional human experience and logical reasoning of governing structures.

Although it is difficult to characterize political theory as a single, linear entity, this paper defines so-called ‘traditional’ works of political theory as theoretical essays, treatises, and books that aim to identify and solve problems of governance. Within these rigidly structured works, it is common to find Enlightenment-inspired modes of philosophical argumentation that follow patterns of logical reasoning and universality similar to strict normative or ethical philosophy. Deductive reasoning, the form of logic that begins with general ideas to reach specific conclusions, is one style of reasoning that was used by many foundational Western political philosophers including Hobbes, Kant, Hegel, Mill, etc.¹ Using rationality to

¹ Radhey Shyam Chaurasia, *History of Western Political Thought* (New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers and Distributors, 2001), 292, 406, 495, 474.

support their specific conclusions, these authors defend their arguments through indisputable or “universal” claims (e.g. Kant’s categorical imperative relies on universal maxims that are derived through reason).² In the Western context, the canon of political theory includes books such as Hobbes’ *Leviathan* and Kant’s *Toward Perpetual Peace: A Philosophical Sketch*, as well as treatises such as Rousseau’s *Social Contract* and Locke’s *Two Treatises on Government*.

Often excluded from said canon are literary or aesthetic (i.e. stylistic or artistically inspired) works of poetry, novels, and passionately emotive investigations of the tangible self and community. Most commonly, their exclusion is due to a perceived failure to follow Western conceptions of rational authority and expressions of feeling that are deemed as ‘unscientific.’ As such, this paper argues that literary or aesthetic works should be read alongside ‘traditional’ canonical texts to broaden politics and gain a better understanding of *human* political establishments and resistance. This is because they better encompass the emotional-rational complexity of the individuals, sociability, and organic dynamics that inform political relationships and institutions.

This paper will begin by complicating the belief that normative or ethical philosophy must be argued within a strict structure by laying the case for aesthetics and literature in

² Immanuel Kant, “Groundwork for the Metaphysics of Morals,” ed. Johnathan Bennett, *Early Modern Texts* (Early Modern Texts, September 2008), <https://www.earlymoderntexts.com/assets/pdfs/kant1785.pdf>, 17.

reasoning,³ moral philosophy, and political relation-building.⁴ Second, this paper will use the framework of inclusive philosophy, or philosophy that incorporates literary and aesthetic elements, to undermine the rigidity of ‘traditional’ political theory by analyzing texts of varying proximity to the canon. Specifically, I will highlight Montesquieu’s *Persian Letters*, Fanon’s *Wretched of the Earth*, and the *Ghazals* of Hafez. This exploration will demonstrate the ability of such works to encompass the political self as it encounters, resists, and builds social or governmental institutions through their use of storytelling or artistic expressions of emotionality. Third, this paper will briefly consider the role literature can play in the expansion of political theory insofar as it adds to the popular conception of what information is politically ‘valuable.’

Aesthetics and Literature in Philosophical Reasoning

Martha Nussbaum argues that literary texts can convey complex human understanding, interpretation, and experiences through their unique manipulation of language, style, and structure.⁵ These thoughts are not expressed to the same degree by the “flat” writing style of many ‘traditional’ philosophical texts⁶ which derive their authority on the matter through their

3 Sarah E. Worth, “Storytelling and Narrative Knowing: An Examination of the Epistemic Benefits of Well-Told Stories,” *Journal of Aesthetic Education* 42, no. 3 (January 2008): pp. 42-56, <https://doi.org/10.2307/25160289>.

4 Martha C. Nussbaum, *Political Emotions: Why Love Matters for Justice* (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2013); Martha C. Nussbaum, “Love’s Knowledge: Essays on Philosophy and Literature,” in *Love’s Knowledge: Essays on Philosophy and Literature* (Oxford University Press, 1990), pp. 3-53.

5 Nussbaum, “Love’s Knowledge,” 3.

6 *Ibid.*

‘universal’ applicability and pure reasoning. By changing their style of writing to indicate a shift between emotive descriptions and more concrete exclamations of the ‘truth,’ literary authors form a nearly tangible world in the minds of their readers that acts as both a basis for their argument and a guide to which ‘truthful’ conclusions are meant to be drawn about the social order.⁷ Thus, as a “practical activity,” philosophical readings of literature can inform an individual’s way of life within the community.⁸

Additionally, novels depicting a family’s adjustment and survival (e.g., Steinbeck’s *Grapes of Wrath*) or the internal dialogue of a person in a vastly different mental state than the reader (e.g., Dostoyevsky’s *Crime and Punishment*) transport the empathetic reader outside of themselves so that they can reflect on their decisions. In response to Nussbaum’s argument and the transportive nature of literature, Sarah E. Worth characterizes the reader as a “judicious spectator” who becomes more moral by spectating another (fictional) being’s emotions.⁹ The turn to becoming “better citizens” in a polity is therefore facilitated by the reader’s exercise in human compassion (or at a minimum, understanding) that results from intimately viewing relationships between others.¹⁰ Worth’s distinction between spectating and participating further reveals the unique opportunity for self-reflection provided by literature.¹¹ Active participation in another person’s decision-making places the

7 *Ibid.*, 8.

8 *Ibid.*, 24.

9 Worth, “Storytelling and Narrative Knowing,” 51.

10 *Ibid.*, 51.

11 *Ibid.*, 49.

participant *outside* the internal world conception of their interlocutor while also giving them a stake in the interaction, thus limiting their potential for self-reflection. Alternately, spectating how another person navigates their surroundings through the eagle-eyed perspective of a novel places the spectator *inside* the psyche of the characters, thus liberating the reader from their own position and increasing their range of empathetic understanding.

Second, literary and aesthetic works should be included in the social study of political theory, given their ability to expand ‘rigid’ moral philosophy and make it easier to practically apply. Structural freedom within literary or aesthetic works allows for deeper engagement with emotionality than permitted by more rigid ‘traditional’ canons of ethical or political theory. Nussbaum acknowledges that the canon of Western liberal political philosophy lacks emotional appeal because rationality is thought to expand liberal autonomy.¹² For example, Locke and Kant are concerned that if emotions are given authority, freedom would be restricted arbitrarily (e.g. an unpleasant reaction to certain opinions may lead to a limit on free speech).¹³ Kant’s calls for universal applicability of norms or theory similarly set precedent for rational decision-making in spite of derailing emotions, as best exemplified by the categorical imperative to act as if that action would become a universal law.¹⁴ However, to engage in truly humane politics, Nussbaum writes, people must overcome narrow notions of

12 Nussbaum, *Political Emotions*, 4.

13 *Ibid.*

14 Kant, “Groundwork for the Metaphysic of Morals,” 23.

universality and expand their circle of concern/community by immersing themselves in “symbols and poetry,” thus revealing where literature and aesthetics fit into the puzzle of political theory.¹⁵

Farah Godrej, in considering the hermeneutics or interpretive language of comparative political theory, notes that the theorist must “*become* one with the ideas in the text” while maintaining enough distance to avoid perpetuating assumptions of mastery undermined by textual misunderstandings.¹⁶ In other words, the political theorist must be able to empathize from the position of an immersed spectator rather than gain authority as a participant. Moreover, issues arising from gaps in the translation of complex cultural/spiritual terms such as Gandhi’s “Atma-darshan”¹⁷ may be minimized as readers of literature immerse themselves more deeply in the contextualized world, relationships, and self-conceptions of their diverse protagonists.

Literature in Political Theory: Montesquieu, Fanon, and Hafez

The works of Montesquieu, Fanon, and Hafez demonstrate some of the ways literature or aesthetic elements can enhance political theory. Montesquieu’s fictional novel, *Persian Letters*, is a particularly salient example because of his position as a ‘traditional’ political theorist who popularized fundamental concepts in liberal politics and wrote canonical

15 Nussbaum, *Political Emotions*, 11.

16 Farah Godrej, “Towards a Cosmopolitan Political Thought: The Hermeneutics of Interpreting the Other,” *Polity* 41, no. 2 (April 2009): pp. 135-165, <https://doi.org/10.1057/pol.2008.28>, 142.

17 *Ibid.*, 146.

treatises (e.g., the separation of powers in his treatise, *The Spirit of Laws*). *Persian Letters* is notable as it criticizes French politics and society through the structure of a travel novel rather than the standard Enlightenment structure of a logically reasoned treatise. Furthermore, Montesquieu deliberately points out the moral failings of decadence by contrasting French and Persian societies through fictional characters, rather than explaining the harms through reasoning. This begs the question, why does Montesquieu create a French self-consciousness through storytelling rather than explicit explanation?

His decision to ‘show, not tell’ the shortcomings of French politics utilizes the emotional appeal of literary style to encourage empathetic spectators to reflect on their political selves when faced with an intimate look into an ‘other.’ To begin, Montesquieu makes two important notes in the preface. First, he anticipates that critics may comment that writing such a novel “is not worthy of a serious man,” thus indicating the widespread exclusion of literature from the canon of highly-regarded theory.¹⁸ Second, he acknowledges the creative liberty he has taken in writing *Persian Letters* by contrasting his proclaimed role as a mere translator with an admission that “all [his] effort has been directed at accommodating the work to our [French] customs and tastes.”¹⁹

Moving into the letters, which constitute the storyline of the novel, Montesquieu introduces the characters of Usbek and Reza. Montesquieu uses Usbek—the older and ‘wiser’ of

18 Charles de Secondat Montesquieu, *Persian Letters*, ed. Margaret Mauldon and Andrew Kahn (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), Preface.

19 *Ibid.*, Preface.

the travelers who write about the differences between French/European and Persian/Asian socio-political culture—to highlight French identity and its flaws. For example, Usbek critically reflects the Christian system back to the French reader by taking on the voice of foreign curiosity, remarking that the “the Christians deemed it less easy to follow these [religious] observances than to appoint bishops who can give dispensations [...]”²⁰ The use of a fictional character in this way allows Montesquieu to bypass the rigidity of rational explanation when trying to criticize the social and political power of the church in France. Instead, he appeals to the instinctual impressions of his reader via the first impressions of his inexperienced character. This strategic literary decision can be understood through Nussbaum’s assertion that authors use characters (e.g., a foreign traveler), style (e.g., phrases indicating confidence in the source of the information, such as “I can consequently assure you”²¹), and structure (e.g., intimate letters between friends) to *illustrate* a series of truths rooted in everyday occurrences rather than theoretical assumptions.

Montesquieu further uses Usbek to reflect on French politics through the same lens of foreign curiosity that enables him to question the ordinary and inspire French self-reflection. In Letter 35, Usbek proclaims to have “studied his [the King of France’s] character and have found in it contradictions which I [Usbek] simply cannot understand; for example, he has a minister who is only eighteen and a mistress who is

20 *Ibid.*, Letter 27.

21 *Ibid.*, Preface.

eighty.”²² This style of writing prompts the reader to turn in on themselves and question the decadence of French politics, foreshadowing Montesquieu’s rebuke of absolute monarchy in later treatises.

Most important, though, is the ability of *Persian Letters* to use the reader’s empathy for Usbek, who the reader becomes deeply acquainted with over the 150 letters, to turn them into a spectator of themselves. Montesquieu’s foreign characters pull the French reader outside their role as a participant in French society and into a position of self-reflection and self-creation as they are invited to view politics from a different perspective. Coupling this with the exotic descriptions of Usbek and Reza as ‘others,’ French readers are prompted to simultaneously distinguish themselves as a unique group and make social or political decisions that would not sound ridiculous when projected back to them. As such, *Persian Letters* demonstrates how literature can enhance political theory by diversifying dominant perspectives and truths through stylistic appeals to human instinct.

Fanon’s *Wretched of the Earth* is a pertinent example of how literary elements can be used as a tool in political theory and how language is itself political. Specifically, Fanon uses varying sentence structures, tones of voice, emotive words, and deliberate spacing of thoughts to create a Black sense of self that is liberated from dominating structures of colonialism. Compared to the self-assured tone and smooth flow of sentences in *Black Skin, White Masks, Wretched of the*

22 *Ibid.*, Letter 35.

Earth is characterized by complex sentences of juxtaposing lengths with numerous semicolons, colons, and consecutive commas. For example, he writes in the first chapter, “On Violence”:

A world compartmentalized, Manichaean and petrified, a world of statues: the statue of the general who led the conquest, the statue of the engineer who built the bridge. A world cocksure of itself, crushing with its stoniness the backbones of those scarred by the whip. That is the colonial world. The colonial subject is a man penned in; apartheid is but one method of compartmentalizing the colonial world.²³

As such, the book conveys a sense of desperation that humanizes both Fanon and his cause, making them more tangible to the empathetic reader. Additionally, the complexity of his sentence structure and dense paragraphs subtly reflect the deeply rooted, meandering, and overwhelming nature of colonialism itself; just as semicolons string together thoughts that are not distinct enough to be discrete sentences, colonialism strings together hopelessly interrelated consequences on the society, economy, and bodies of the colonized. In this way, Fanon begins to cement his foundation of truths more profoundly than otherwise possible in the more “flat”²⁴ style of ‘traditional’ political theory, preparing the reader for a more open reception of his consequent argument.

Furthermore, Fanon uses the language of violence to expose the spectating reader to the “pure violence” of the colonizers, making them sympathetic to the plight of

23 Frantz Fanon, *The Wretched of the Earth*, ed. Richard Philcox (New York: Grove Press, 2021), 35.

24 Nussbaum, *Political Emotions*, 3.

the colonized. Shocking words about the colonizers such as “destroy,” “demolish,” “bury,” and “banish” serve to remove the colonist from the nation and provide his Black interlocutors with the space to create an authentic sense of self.²⁵ By wielding the power of emotive language, Fanon speaks to the human being at the very heart of political theory, acknowledging their dual emotional-rational nature as it builds their relationship with themselves and the dominating institutions imposed on them. This is made more clear by his humanization of the African nation itself through words that are generally used to denote violence against humanity, such as “raping” and “starving.”²⁶ In doing so, Fanon elicits the type of emotional empathy that catalyzes action against oppressive systems of rational complacency and reveals an incredibly nuanced understanding of the political as one of institutionalized social relationships.²⁷ Perhaps the most telling amalgamation of these techniques is Fanon’s exclamation, “In reality, to hell with him.”²⁸ Separated by a comma that indicates a break in this perception, Fanon indicates a readiness to draw upon his illustration of the truth with the transition, “in reality,” before unleashing a rare wave of passion with the conclusion, “to hell with him [the colonizer].” In a short sentence, Fanon moves past the isolated political theory of rational philosophers to realize the passion held by the everyday individual at the heart of politics. Therefore, his writing becomes a form of embodied

25 Fanon, *The Wretched of the Earth*, 31.

26 *Ibid.*, 34.

27 *Ibid.*

28 *Ibid.*, 33.

resistance itself that has left a lasting impact on decolonial works and academia.

Finally, Hafez's poetry in *Ghazals* illustrates the way aesthetic works of literature that are not considered to be connected to political theory in the Western context can still explore highly political expressions of the self, relation to others, and relation with the state. Hafez, a Persian poet living in the 14th century, is a part of the Sufi tradition that takes a spiritual view of God and ecstatic love. He was not a political theorist, nor was his poetry read as political works. Yet, his *ghazals*, or mystical poems about love and the self, provide insight into the dynamics of social and political relationships with authority and institutions. Hafez's self is created through an artistic conversation between the highest spiritual authority (i.e. the mystical/spiritual divine) and the worldly authorities who seek to impose their own perspectives onto the polity. For example, in ghazal 80, Hafez announces his resistance to conformity and appreciation for individuality with the lines "Whether I'm good or bad, you judge yourself" and "Behind the veil, who is good, who the freak?"²⁹ Rather than painting a detailed picture of the other, Hafez leaves it ambiguous yet personal, referring to it as "you" while never providing explicit details as to the constitution of the character itself. As such, he does not give the reader a chance to participate as an interlocutor, rather, the reader is permitted to spectate Hafez's self-confidence so they can then question their own self-presentation. Moreover, his use of poetic metaphors and

29 Hafez, "Ghazaliyat of Hafiz," ed. Shahriar Shahriari, *Ghazaliyat of Hafiz*, 2015, <http://www.hafizonlove.com/divan/>, Ghazal 80.

Sufi imagery in sentences such as “Hafez, on your deathbed, bring the cup to your cheek”³⁰ (cup referring to wine and the intoxication with love for God) invite the reader into an intimate world that is just vague enough to let their imagination paint between the lines with the details with their own environment and identity.³¹ Hafez’s condemnation of those who judge others is also just as political as it is social, especially as he refers to kings and religious authorities, thus demonstrating the ability of aesthetics to guide spectating readers into better citizens. Therefore, it can be seen that literary-aesthetic or artistic works are valuable insofar as they add diverse perspectives about the relationships political actors hold with themselves and structures of authority that make political *theory* more true to the nuances of political *reality*.

Conclusion

The inclusion of literary or aesthetic works such as those discussed can help to expand political theory by moving it away from the rigidity of Western Enlightenment rationality. In doing so, political theory becomes more representative of the subjects it studies—human beings who are constantly defining and redefining their relationships with themselves, others, and authorities. If the goal of political theory is truly to “get others’ thought right *on its own terms*,” as argued by Mark Warren, then an expansion of its canon to encompass more humanistic elements will provide context that is only accessible to the spectating reader.³² This context is present as Montesquieu’s

30 *Ibid.*

31 *Ibid.*

32 Melissa S. Williams and Mark E. Warren, “A Democratic Case for Comparative Political Theory,” *Political Theory* 42, no. 1 (2013): pp. 26-57, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0090591713507934>, 35.

Usbek reflects the world of French politics back to the French reader without the haze of personal motivation, Fanon's language of passion and violence reframes colonialism from the lived perspective of the colonized African, and Hafez's Sufi imagery paints a picture of spiritual love that informs a Persian self that is not afraid to resist human authority.

In conclusion, by telling the story of the people and institutions that constitute political society, literary authors invite their readers into the liberating position of a spectator who can reflect back on themselves and their theories without the pressure of isolated rationalism. Stylistic manipulations of language and aesthetic expressions of complex feelings such as love, resistance, or anger allow the author to engage with the political human as they model a nuanced vision of the truth that can be compared with previously held conceptions of the self and its institutional relationships. In this way, the aesthetics of literature represents and analyzes the duality of emotion and reason that colors human navigation of their personal, institutional, and governmental relations. As such, a broader, reflexive political theory must openly embrace the works that return the study of politics to the polity at the heart of the grand polis.

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